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Designing sensor technology for estimating CO₂
reductions through the adoption and use of improved
cookstoves

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ABSTRACT

Climate change is a critical global issue, prompting the establishment of CO₂ certificate trading under the Paris Agreement to incentivize emissions reductions. The effectiveness of these certificates relies on accurate and reliable measurement of saved emissions. This thesis details the design and implementation of a data logging system that quantifies the environmental impact of improved cookstoves in comparison to traditional models. The system is open-source, reliable, and cost-effective, utilizing a Raspberry Pi Pico microcontroller to collect data from a thermocouple and a scale. These sensors measure the runtime and wood consumption of cookstoves.

The system is specifically designed for deployment in remote regions without electricity or Wi-Fi connectivity. It relies on solar power and utilizes cellular communication to transmit sensor data to a cloud-based server, ensuring continuous and autonomous operation. By providing precise and reliable data, the system enhances the accuracy of emissions calculations associated with cookstoves. This thesis serves as a comprehensive guide for creating a robust, cost-efficient, and remotely deployable data logging solution, contributing to the accurate assessment of CO₂ emissions savings and supporting climate change mitigation efforts.

1 INTRODUCTION

The trading of CO₂ certificates has gained prominence following the Paris Agreement, which aims to limit the global temperature increase to a maximum of 2°C above pre-industrial levels. One of Switzerland’s strategies to meet its climate commitments involves financing a clean cooking project that promotes the adoption of improved cookstoves. The objective of this initiative is to distribute 200,000 improved cookstoves to urban and peri-urban households, generating 1 million Internationally Transferred Mitigation Outcomes (ITMOs) for sale to Switzerland over a seven-year period. However, multiple studies have highlighted that these ITMOs are often based on inaccurate assumptions (Beyene *et al.*, 2015; Gill-Wiehl *et al.*, 2024; West *et al.*, 2023). The reliability of the entire system depends on the accuracy of the ITMOs. Without precise estimations, the credibility and effectiveness of the trading mechanism are compromised.

1.1 Cookstoves

Reducing emissions from household cooking is a key strategy in mitigating global greenhouse gas emissions (“AR6 Synthesis Report”, n.d.). In many rural regions, including Malawi, traditional cooking methods rely on an open fire with three stones to support the cooking pot. This inefficient combustion process results in high fuel consumption and significant emissions (““We threw away the stones”: a mixed method ... | Wellcome Open Research”, n.d.; Gill-Wiehl *et al.*, 2024; West *et al.*, 2023). Improved cookstoves are designed to enhance combustion efficiency and minimize waste heat. In addition to the environmental benefits, improved cookstoves contribute to better health outcomes by lowering exposure to harmful pollutants indoors. The reduction in emissions achieved through these cookstoves is quantified and traded as Internationally Transferred Mitigation Outcomes (ITMOs).

Achieving global climate targets requires precise and reliable measurements of emission reductions facilitated by these technologies.

1.2 Research Objectives

The selection and placement of sensors were previously developed by Louis Ambühl (Ambühl, 2024). This thesis builds upon his work by focusing on the practical deployment and implementation of these monitoring systems. To achieve this, the following objectives have been defined:

- Design and assembly of the hardware components
- Development of a comprehensive wiring diagram
- Implementation of microcontroller code
- Establishment of a robust server connection
- Development of an open-source, reliable, and cost-effective system
- Defining a Standard Operating Procedure (SOP)

These objectives are encapsulated in the following research questions:

- **What is the most reliable and cost-effective method for remotely measuring cook-stove usage time and fuel consumption?**
- **What are the optimal methods for saving and storing the collected data?**

1.3 Scope and Limitations

This thesis focuses on the design and development of a cellular-network-based data logger equipped with integrated memory storage, a temperature sensor, and a scale. The system is intended to enable global data accessibility by synchronizing it to a dedicated server.

The scope of this thesis is restricted to the technical development of the data logging system, including hardware integration, firmware implementation, and server communication. This study does not include behavioral analyses, long-term field testing, or user adoption studies, which are recommended for future research.

By focusing on low-cost and open-source solutions, this thesis aims to make data loggers widely accessible and adaptable for a global audience, thereby helping with future deployments.

1.4 Detail design of Previous Work

Previous studies employed similar methods, monitoring fire temperature and fuel consumption by measuring the weight of wood burned during cooking (Miller *et al.*, 2022; Ventrella & MacCarty, 2019). However, these studies encountered several critical technical limitations:

- **Sensor Data Loss:** Poor installation and reflective surfaces on metallic chimneys led to unreliable temperature measurements.
- **Limited Monitoring Scope:** Existing systems could not track multiple cookstoves within a household.
- **Lack of Data Automation:** No integrated analytics platform for processing and analyzing collected data.
- **User Inconsistencies:** Unclear usage instructions resulted in variations in system operation.

1.5 Justification

Enhancing reliability and developing an open-source system with the flexibility to accommodate additional sensors ensure a more robust and adaptable solution. Such a system lays the foundation for future projects to leverage the data logging framework for diverse applications.

Furthermore, incorporating automated data upload to a centralized server enables seamless integration with tools such as Excel or MATLAB for further analysis. This functionality represents a critical step towards creating a scalable and efficient data management environment.

These objectives are fundamental to the success of this thesis and are essential for achieving its intended impact.

2 METHODS

The objective of this study is to design and construct a system capable of monitoring and recording data related to cookstove usage. This data must be transmitted to a centralized server for further processing and analysis. To achieve this, system's modularity is ensured; each subsystem addresses a specific aspect of functionality.

2.1 System Overview

The data logger is composed of five primary physical subsystems, each performing a specific function in the overall operation of the device, as illustrated in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1. Schematic representation of the five physical subsystems comprising the data logger.

These subsystems are detailed as follows:

1. **Data Acquisition:** Responsible for capturing and amplifying sensor signals to ensure accurate and reliable data collection.
2. **Power Management:** Provides stable and sufficient power to support the continuous operation of all other subsystems.
3. **Data Storage:** Facilitates the local storage of collected data on an SD card and ensures secure synchronization with a cloud-based platform.

- 4. **Microcontroller:** Functions as the central processing unit, orchestrating the operation and interaction of all physical subsystems.
- 5. **Real-Time Clock (RTC):** Supplies precise timekeeping to the microcontroller, enabling accurate timestamping of all recorded data.

In addition to the physical subsystems, the data logger integrates two software-based components that are essential for its functionality:

- 6. **Software Design:** Governs the functionality of all physical subsystems by coordinating their interactions and managing system-level operations. The software architecture is illustrated in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2. Diagram of the software architecture controlling the physical subsystems.

- 7. **Server Structure:** Facilitates the secure storage, accessibility, and sharing of synchronized data in the cloud. The server structure and data flow are depicted in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3. Overview of the server structure and its role in cloud-based data synchronization .

2.2 Software Used

The development and deployment of the data logger's software require specific tools. The firmware for the data logger is developed using **Thonny**, an Integrated Development Environment (IDE) optimized for Python-based microcontroller programming. Thonny was selected for its lightweight interface, built-in debugging tools, and seamless compatibility with the Raspberry Pi Pico.

The data logger transmits sensor data to a cloud-based server for real-time monitoring and storage. The server infrastructure is built on **ThingSpeak**, a cloud platform designed for Internet of Things (IoT) applications. ThingSpeak enables the efficient management of API requests through customizable data channels, ensuring reliable data synchronization. Additionally, its real-time visualization tools and MATLAB integration provide advanced data analysis capabilities, making it well-suited for this application.

The hardware schematics and wiring diagrams for the system were designed using **EasyEDA**, an electronic design automation (EDA) tool.

2.3 Design Considerations

This section explains the critical factors that informed the design choices for each subsystem of the data logger. These decisions were guided by evaluation of performance, cost-effectiveness, reliability, and adaptability to diverse operating conditions. By addressing these considerations, the system aims to achieve optimal functionality while maintaining feasibility for widespread deployment.

2.3.1 Data Acquisition

The foundation of this subsystem is built upon the integration of a thermocouple and a load cell, selected for measuring temperature and weight, respectively. These sensors require signal amplification to ensure accurate and interpretable data. To achieve this, amplifiers with well-documented and widely utilized libraries were chosen, ensuring reliability, ease of implementation, and compatibility with the system architecture.

2.3.2 Power Management

The power management subsystem is designed to ensure reliable and continuous operation of the data logger. To meet these requirements, solar panels were selected as the power source, offering robustness and adaptability across varying environmental conditions. It must

accommodate peak current demands during data upload and sustain system functionality for a minimum of four days without the connection to a power source such as solar panels to ensure sufficient battery life during cloudy periods.

After selecting the components for the power management subsystem, key operational parameters were defined as follows:

- **Runtime:** At least four days of continuous operation without a power source.
- **Peak Power:** 15 Watts to handle the maximum current demands during data transmission.
- **Average Power:** 0.2 Watts during regular operation.

To estimate the required battery capacity, Equation 2.1 was used, incorporating a safety factor of 2 to account for variations in environmental conditions and system performance:

$$\text{Capacity [Wh]} = \text{Power [W]} \times \text{hours per day [h/d]} \times \text{days [d]} \times \text{safety factor} \quad (2.1)$$

Based on this calculation, the battery capacity was estimated at 40 Wh. The size of the solar panels was determined by evaluating their performance under low-light conditions, specifically on cloudy days in Switzerland. To ensure sufficient energy generation, the solar panels were designed to provide at least 15 Wh/day, meeting the system's average energy consumption with a 200 % margin. This accounts for potential degradation or failure of individual solar cells.

2.3.3 Data Storage

The data storage subsystem must store collected data locally on the device and transmit it to a server for further analysis. To achieve this, the most reliable, cost-effective, and straightforward solution is the use of an SD card for local data storage. The SD card ensures compatibility, durability, and ease of access, making it an ideal choice for the device.

For cloud synchronization, in regions lacking consistent access to power and Ethernet connections, two potential approaches were considered for transmitting data to the server: cellular networks and satellite communication. While satellite communication offers the advantage of location independence by eliminating the need for cellular network coverage, it has significant drawbacks, including higher power consumption and costs.

Cellular network-based communication was selected due to its balance of reliability, cost efficiency, and lower power requirements. Simcom **SIM7600E module** was chosen as the communication interface. This module is affordable, widely available, and supports the essential bandwidths required for reliable data transmission to the cloud.

2.3.4 Microcontroller

The selection of an appropriate microcontroller is a crucial aspect of system design, as it serves as the central processing unit responsible for coordinating all subsystems. Initial prototyping and testing was performed using an Arduino, a platform known for its robustness, acceptance, and extensive library support. However, two significant limitations were identified: limited memory capacity and relatively high cost.

To address these constraints, the **Raspberry Pi Pico** was selected for the final implementation. This microcontroller offers several advantages, including a compact form factor, low power consumption and cost-effectiveness while maintaining sufficient computational capability.

2.3.5 Real-Time Clock (RTC)

The Real-Time Clock (RTC) is essential for providing precise timekeeping to the microcontroller, ensuring accurate timestamps of recorded data. After evaluating various RTC modules, it was determined that differences in functionality, reliability and power efficiency were negligible. As a consequence, the decision was influenced by quality of the library and availability of the module.

2.3.6 Software Design

Ensuring software reliability is a critical component of the data logger's functionality. Two primary software processes were identified as potential points of failure: managing data storage on the SD card and uploading data to the ThingSpeak cloud platform.

To address these challenges, different data formats were employed based on the specific requirements of each task:

- **SD Card Storage:** Data is stored locally on the SD card in **CSV (Comma-Separated Values)** format because of simplicity, ease of implementation, and compatibility with streaming data. By writing data incrementally to the file, the design avoids the loading of the entire dataset into memory, thereby minimizing memory-related issues and ensuring efficient use of the microcontroller's resources.
- **ThingSpeak Data Upload:** For transmitting data to the ThingSpeak cloud platform, **JSON (JavaScript Object Notation)** format is used. JSON provides a structured, hierarchical format that is easy to append and process, making it well-suited for bulk data uploads.

This design ensures a robust and efficient approach to managing and transmitting data while addressing the specific reliability challenges posed by each subsystem.

2.3.7 Server Structure

The server infrastructure is responsible for managing, storing, and providing access to the collected data. For this purpose, **ThingSpeak** was selected as the cloud platform due to its ease of implementation, cost-effectiveness, and scalability.

By using ThingSpeak, the server structure ensures reliable and low-cost data handling while maintaining flexibility for integration with Matlab.

2.4 Power consumption test setup

To obtain precise power consumption data, the testing process was divided into two distinct experiments:

- **Experiment 1: Current measurement for the SIM7600E Module**

The first experiment focused on measuring the current drawn by the SIM7600E with a voltage of 5V during various operational states. This approach allowed for the identification of current spikes corresponding to specific actions.

- **Experiment 2: Current measurement for the entire system**

The second experiment involved measuring the current consumption supplied at 3.3V of the complete system, excluding the SIM7600E module. This provided understanding of the base power requirements of the remaining subsystems under typical operating conditions.

These measurements were conducted under controlled conditions to ensure accuracy and repeatability. The resulting data enabled the calculation of long-term battery life under controlled conditions, excluding factors such as battery degradation and temperature variations.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Hardware

The hardware for the data logger was designed to ensure modularity, reliability, and compatibility with the required sensors and subsystems. The following materials were selected:

- **Microcontroller (Raspberry Pi Pico):** Manages data acquisition, processing, and transmission.
- **Data Storage (SD Card Module & SD Card):** Stores sensor data locally.
- **Cellular Modem (SIM7670E):** Enables reliable data transmission over cellular networks.
- **Weight Sensor (Load Cell & HX711 Amplifier):** Measures the weight of wood consumed by the cookstove.
- **Temperature Sensor (K-Type Thermocouple & AD8495 Amplifier):** Records cookstove temperature for runtime analysis.
- **Real-Time Clock (PCF8523):** Provides precise timestamps for recorded data.
- **Power Management Module (Waveshare Solar Power Module D):** Regulates power from batteries and solar panels for continuous operation.
- **Battery Pack (Three 18650 Li-ion Batteries):** Stores energy with high efficiency.
- **Solar Panels (Two 10 W, 12 V Panels):** Generate renewable energy to charge the batteries in remote locations.
- **Voltage Regulator (LM3940):** Converts 5 V input to 3.3 V for component compatibility.
- **Enclosure (TRU COMPONENTS KST 220):** Protects internal electronics from environmental exposure and damage.

Figure 3.1. Schematic representation of the hardware connections.

The schematic representation of the hardware connections is shown in Figure 3.1. This diagram provides an overview of how the components are integrated.

For detailed assembly, the wiring diagram is provided in Figure 3.2. This diagram outlines the specific connections required for each component. More information is provided in the appendix A.3.

Figure 3.2. Wiring diagram generated with EasyEDA.

3.2 Software

The software powering the data logger is designed to ensure efficient data collection and transmission. The primary program operates during data logging, coordinating sensor data acquisition, timestamping, local storage, and transmission to the cloud. The complete source code is accessible in the Appendix A.2.

The following scripts must be executed to prepare the system for operation:

- **RTC Setup:** Configures the Real-Time Clock (RTC).
- **Load Cell Calibration:** Delivers values which need to be transferred to the main file.
- **Thermocouple Test:** Verifies the functionality and accuracy of the thermocouple.

3.2.1 Main code

To ensure precise measurements at regular intervals, the main code is designed to operate without interruptions. The primary program employs a repetitive main loop, where only a single step of the process is executed at a time during data saving or updating. This modular approach minimizes delays and ensures smooth data collection and transmission.

Algorithm 3.1 Main Program Loop

```
1: Initialize: Load Cell, Thermocouple, SD Card, SIM7670E Module
2: Set: Crucial parameters for operation
3: while True do
4:   Retrieve current time
5:   if a new day begins then
6:     Create a new CSV file
7:   end if
8:   if it is time to update data on the SD card then
9:     Update the JSON file
10:  end if
11:  if it is time to upload data to ThingSpeak then
12:    Upload data to ThingSpeak
13:  end if
14:  if the SIM7670E module is not in use then
15:    Put the SIM7670E module in sleep mode
16:  end if
17:  if too many entries exist in the JSON file due to connection errors then
18:    Delete excess entries
19:  end if
20: end while
```

The most critical part of the program is the data upload to ThingSpeak. Communication between the microcontroller and the SIMCOM module is managed using AT Commands, which can be found in the appendix A.4. The upload process is divided into steps, with the function being called repeatedly to handle bulk data uploads. This ensures a non-blocking approach to data transmission.

Algorithm 3.2 Upload_Step Function

```

1: function UPLOAD_STEP(ThingSpeakData)
2:   Initialize: Current_Time ← GETCURRENTTIME
3:           ▷ Check the current upload state and execute corresponding actions
4:   if Upload_State = 0 then
5:     if not SUCCESSFULATCOMMAND(Initial Command) then
6:       Upload_Success ← False
7:     end if
8:     Last_Upload_Time_Holder ← Current_Time
9:   else if Iterating through AT Commands (States 0–last) then
10:    Execute the corresponding tasks for each state
11:  else if Upload_State = last then
12:    if not SUCCESSFULATCOMMAND(Final Command) then
13:      Upload_Success ← False
14:    end if
15:    if Upload is successful then
16:      Reset states, clear JSON file, and perform garbage collection
17:      Update the last upload time
18:    else
19:      Restart from Upload_State = 0
20:    end if
21:  end if
22:  Increment Upload_State by 1
23: end function

```

3.2.2 Setting the RTC

To ensure accurate timestamping by the microcontroller, the Real-Time Clock (RTC) must be configured with the correct time. This process involves synchronizing the RTC with the current time of the computer to which the system is connected. The provided script initializes and sets the RTC.

3.2.3 Load Cell Calibration

The output values from the load cell amplifier vary depending on the number and type of load cells used in the scale, as well as the scale's inherent weight. To ensure accurate measurements, the system requires calibration.

The calibration process involves two steps:

- Ensure that the scale is empty and record the raw value as the baseline measurement.
- Place a known weight on the scale and input its value into the program. Using this information, the system calculates the raw value and derives the calibration factor for accurate weight measurement.

This calibration process is essential to account for variations in hardware configurations and to ensure reliable weight measurements during operation.

3.3 System Cost

Table 3.1. Component cost breakdown in CHF

Component	Price [CHF]
RP Pico	3.90
Micro SD Card	4.50
Micro SD Card Module	4.90
SIM7670E	26.50
Load Cells + HX711	18.05
Thermocouple	23.00
K-Type Connector	5.52
Thermocouple Amplifier	10.85
Power Management Module	11.75
Batteries	26.70
Solar Panels	25.00
LM3940	1.43
TRU COMPONENTS KST 220	12.20
Connection Sleeve	4.50
Cables	3.00
Total	181.80

The prices presented in this work are based on Swiss suppliers. However, many of the components can be sourced at a lower cost from international suppliers. Comparable devices, such as the SenseCAP Sensor Hub (“SenseCAP Sensor Hub 4G Data Logger - with built-in rechargeable battery version”, n.d.), typically exceed the price of the proposed device, even without the inclusion of sensors and solar panels.

3.4 Power Consumption

The power consumption of the system varies depending on the operational tasks being performed. The current draw of the Raspberry Pi peaks during data synchronization with the SD card, as illustrated in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3. Average current spike observed during data synchronization to the SD card.

Similarly, significant current spikes occur in the SIMCOM module during the data upload process, as shown in Figure 3.4.

From the graphical data, the base power consumption of the system (excluding data saving or uploading processes) is measured at 188 mW. By integrating the observed current spikes over time, the energy consumption for specific operations is calculated as follows:

- **Data saving to SD card:** 46 μ Wh per operation.
- **Data upload to ThingSpeak:** 600 μ Wh per operation.

Assuming a typical operating cycle where data is uploaded to ThingSpeak every two minutes and saved to the SD card three times per minute, the daily energy consumption of the system is approximately 5.2 Wh. Based on this figure, the system’s battery can sustain operation for seven days without solar panel support.

Figure 3.4. Average current spike observed during data upload to ThingSpeak.

This analysis demonstrates the system’s efficiency in power usage and highlights its ability for operation in remote environments, even under conservative conditions. These findings underline the system’s robustness and suitability for remote deployments where reliable energy sources are limited.

For detailed data analysis, the complete data sets are provided in the appendix: [A.1](#)

3.5 Standard Operating Procedure (SOP)

3.5.1 Installation and Setup

For optimal performance and longevity, the device and its sensors must be installed in a location protected from water exposure and prolonged ultraviolet (UV) radiation. The thermocouple should be positioned according to the methodology outlined in Ambuehl’s thesis ([Ambühl, 2024](#)), ensuring precise temperature measurements. The load cells must be suspended from a stable beam with a secure attachment to facilitate accurate weighing of the wood prior to combustion.

The solar panels should be mounted in an open, flat area devoid of obstructions such as grass, trees, or other objects that could cast shadows, as shading can significantly reduce efficiency.

Before deployment, the system should be fully charged. This can be achieved by connecting a USB-C cable to the Power Management Module to ensure sufficient initial battery capacity.

A functional Machine-to-Machine (M2M) SIM card, appropriate for the designated region, must be inserted into the device.

To ensure the accuracy of collected data, all sensors must be calibrated and tested before field deployment. This process involves executing every test script and verifying data integrity by checking the SD card and the cloud server for successful data collection.

Once testing is complete, the system should be completely powered down to ensure a fresh restart upon deployment.

As a final verification step, the accuracy of the system should be reviewed in a fully assembled setup by checking the sensor readings remotely via the online monitoring platform.

3.5.2 Software Configuration

The following software parameters must be customized for each device prior to deployment:

- **API Key:** Retrieve the unique API key from the ThingSpeak platform.
- **Channel ID:** Identify and assign the correct channel ID from the ThingSpeak account.
- **Measurement Interval:** Define the frequency at which sensor readings are taken.
- **Data Storage Interval:** Specify the number of recorded measurements before data is written to the SD card.
- **Data Upload Interval:** Set the frequency of data transmission to the ThingSpeak server.
- **Load Cell Calibration:** Update the tare value and calibration factor based on the results obtained from the load cell calibration procedure.

3.5.3 Device Operation

The primary responsibility of participating households is to place the wood intended for combustion onto the scale. Individual pieces can then be removed as needed for burning. This approach ensures gradual variations in measured values, allowing for an extended measurement interval without compromising data accuracy.

The only required troubleshooting procedure for participants is a power cycle, wherein the device should be restarted in the event of operational issues.

To ensure continued functionality and reliability, all deployed devices must be remotely monitored via the cloud platform. This enables early detection of potential malfunctions and facilitates intervention when necessary.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This thesis has successfully designed and implemented a cost-effective, reliable, and open-source cellular data logger. The system provides a robust solution for the subsystems: data acquisition, power management, data storage, microcontroller integration, real-time clock (RTC), software design, and server infrastructure. The device demonstrated reliability by successfully uploading data to a cloud-based server continuously for four days.

The monitoring device enables effective tracking of cookstove performance in remote regions, with seamless access to the collected data via the ThingSpeak platform. Furthermore, the power consumption measurements allow for precise runtime calculations in controlled laboratory environments.

The entire source code and related resources are available in the following repository [A.2](#).

To advance this project and enable the deployment of multiple cookstove data loggers in Malawi, the following steps are recommended:

- Enhance the enclosure design to develop a waterproof and weather- and UV-resistant casing.
- Conduct real-world testing in remote regions to verify reliability and robustness under diverse conditions.
- Optimize the hardware by incorporating a 555 timer IC to enable remote device resets.
- Implement automatic data analytics to retrieve the Runtime and wood consumption.
- Facilitate a production process to facilitate mass deployment of the devices.

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A.1 Power Consumption Files

The complete dataset is provided in the supplementary files and can be accessed at:

- [Power Consumption of SIM7670E](#)
- [Power Consumption of complete system excluding SIM7670E](#)

A.2 GitHub Repository

The complete source code, including all scripts, configuration files, and documentation necessary for system implementation, is hosted in a publicly accessible GitHub repository. The repository is structured to facilitate ease of use, with separate directories for firmware and hardware schematics. Users can access the repository through the following link:

[GitHub Repository](#)

A.3 PCB Files

The files were created using [EasyEDA](#). All the files necessary to continue this project are provided on GitHub under [PCB-files](#)

A.4 AT-Commands

All the AT-Commands can be found on the GitHub under [AT-Commands](#).